

Spatial Analysis of Urban Tree Composition, Diversity and Richness in the Built Up Area Landuse of University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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Abstract : The study investigated the spatial analysis of urban tree composition, diversity and richness in the built up area of University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Four quadrats of 25m x 25m size were laid randomly in each of the three parks and inventories of trees $\geq 10\text{cm}$ girth at breast height were taken and used to calculate the species composition, diversity and richness. Results showed that species composition and diversity in Abuja Park was the highest with 134 species and 0.866 respectively while the species richness was highest in Choba Park with a value of 2.496. The correlation between the size of park (spatial coverage) and species composition was 0.99 while the correlation between the size of the park and species diversity was 0.78. There was direct relationship between species composition and diversity while the relationship between species composition and species richness was inversely proportional. Rational use of these resources is encouraged.

Keywords : Built up area, composition, diversity, richness, spatial analysis, urban tree.

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